

Calf circumference as a predictor of dementia and mild cognitive impairment: A meta-analysis.

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Abstract:

Calf circumference (CC) is a simple and reliable measure of muscle mass, but literature on the relationship between CC and dementia is scarce. This meta-analysis aimed to assess CC as a predictor of dementia and mild cognitive impairment. We searched PubMed/MEDLINE, Cochrane Library, and the first 100 articles in Google Scholar, with no date limitation (up to May 2026). The keywords calf circumference, dementia, cognitive dysfunction, cognitive decline, cognitive impairment, and Alzheimer's disease were used. The search included references of the selected studies. The name of the authors, author's name, and country, year of publication, calf circumference among cases and controls, and the association of dementia and calf circumference were collected. Three hundred-nine studies were found, 103 remained after duplication removal, 28 full texts were checked and eight studies (8241 participants) were eligible for meta-analysis. The study found a negative association of calf circumference with dementia, Mean difference, -2.28. 95% CI, -4.23 to -.052, and P-value for overall effect, 0.01. However, substantial heterogeneity was evident, I^2 for heterogeneity, 99%, P-value < 0.00001. The chi-square was 659.52. The negative association of calf circumference and dementia remained robust after removing the study with the highest heterogeneity, MD, -1.23. 95% CI, -1.48 to -.97, and P-value for overall effect < 0.001, and Z score = 9.48. No significant heterogeneity was found $I^2 = 22%$, P-value, 0.28. The chi-square was 3.83. Calf circumference is negatively associated with cognitive decline; further studies focusing on calf circumference/waist circumference ratio are needed.

Keywords: calf circumference, dementia, cognitive decline, cognitive fragility.

Introduction:

Dementia is ranked among the top three causes of disability and the fifth cause of mortality over the globe. Fifty million people are suffering from this chronic disease and the number is increasing with a negative impact on the patients, their families, the healthcare system, and the whole community.¹⁻³

Overweight and obesity are increasingly recognized health issue with significant impact of patients, healthcare system, and the community. With two-trillion US dollars annual expenses and the projection of 1.35 billion overweight and 573 million obese, obesity and overweight are real nightmare.⁴

Obesity is an age-related chronic disease that can negatively affect the neurocognitive function. Obesity is associated with cognitive especially among the aging population with obesity-related metabolic consequences. In addition, anthropometric measurements of obesity are linked to poor neural integrity and Brain atrophy.⁵ Dementia is extremely disabling and there is limited success regarding its treatment despite the great therapeutic advances. Therefore, the identification of dementia-modifiable risk factors is crucial for prevention, earlier detection, and management.^{6, 7}

A significant health issue of the current society is muscle mass (MM), the interplay of skeletal muscle and disease is complex and multifactorial, and muscle atrophy is associated with dementia, diabetes, fracture, low bone mineral density, and malnutrition. Because of this MM disorder significantly influence the patients quality of life.⁸

The proportion of elder adults (age ≥ 60 years) is expected to reach 20 percent by the year 2050; this is mirrored by a dramatic increase in dementia.⁹ Importantly, fat distribution differ in young and aging population, a study conducted in the USA found that waist circumference but not body mass index is associated with cognitive dysfunction.¹⁰

The association between body mass index and obesity is not uniform, a decreased cognitive function was observed among those who are <75 years and who maintained normal body mass index and were overweight, and the contrary was observed among those who were older.¹¹ In addition, body mass variability, and high waist circumference loss are associated with faster cognitive decline.¹²

Calf circumference (CC) is a simple and practical tool for skeletal muscle mass and sarcopenia, cut-off values were developed (34 and 32 for males, and 33 and 31 for females for moderate and severe low CC respectively).¹³ Low calf circumference is associated with high mortality in hospital settings, outpatients, and nursing homes.¹⁴ In addition. Calf circumference, when used with other parameters improved the diagnostic accuracy of sarcopenia and is correlated with both cardiovascular and all-cause mortality.¹⁵ Calf circumference is more accurate in long-term predicting mortality in the elderly than body mass index.¹⁶ Literature on calf circumference and

cognitive decline is scarce. To the best of my knowledge, no previous meta-analysis assessed the relationship between cognitive decline and calf circumference. Therefore we went ahead to assess the association between low calf circumference and cognitive decline.

Materials and Methods:

Eligibility criteria according to PICOS:

The current meta-analysis was conducted during April and May 2026 according to the PRISMA Guidelines.

Inclusion criteria:

Studies were included if they were retrospective, prospective cohorts, case-control studies, or cross-sectional studies evaluating the association between calf circumference and dementia.

Exclusion criteria:

Case reports, case series, and studies on animals were excluded.

People: Adults with dementia.

Comparators: Adults without dementia

Outcome measure:

The outcome measure was the association of calf circumference and dementia.

Types of dementia assessed:

Alzheimer, mild cognitive decline, and cognitive frailty were assessed, the methods of assessment were Mini-Mental State Examination Montreal Cognitive Assessment.

Literature search and data extraction:

Two independent authors systematically searched PubMed/MEDLINE, Web of Science, Cochrane Library, and the first 100 results retrieved from Google Scholar for eligible studies, with no restriction on publication date. Only English-language articles published up to May 25, 2026 were considered. The search strategy used combinations of the keywords “calf circumference” AND (“dementia” OR “cognitive

dysfunction” OR “cognitive decline” OR “cognitive impairment” OR “Alzheimer’s disease”).

The study selection process is summarized in Supplementary Table S1. A total of 309 records were identified through database searching. After removal of 106 duplicate records, 103 studies remained for title and abstract screening. Of these, 28 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility, and 8 studies, comprising 8,047 participants, met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final meta-analysis.

Data extraction:

Data extraction was performed independently by two authors using a standardized data collection form. Extracted information included study characteristics, participant demographics, calf circumference measurements, cognitive outcomes, and relevant effect estimates. Any discrepancies between reviewers were resolved through discussion and consensus.

Calf circumference measurement:

In this study, calf circumference was recorded in $\text{cm} \pm \text{SD}$ and dementia of all types was included in Tables, 1-3 and Figures 1.

Risk of bias assessment:

The Newcastle Ottawa Scale was used to assess the quality of the included studies ^[17].

Statistical analysis:

Statistical analyses were performed using Review Manager (RevMan) software. Pooled effect estimates were calculated using the DerSimonian and Laird random-effects model to account for anticipated between-study variability, as all included studies were observational in design and substantial heterogeneity was expected.

Continuous outcome data (calf circumference measurements) were manually entered and analyzed using mean differences (MDs) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs). A P-value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Figure 1. The association of calf circumference and dementia.

Table 1. Basic characteristics of patients with cognitive decline.

Author	Methods	Dementia type	Age	Cognitive assessment
Cova et al. 2017 ^[18]	Cross-sectional	Alzheimer's and mild cognitive decline	>70 years	Mini-Mental State Examination
He et al. 2024 ^[19]	Cross-sectional	Alzheimer's disease	>65 years	National Institute of Aging and Alzheimer's Association criteria
Kim et al. 2019 ^[20]	Cross-sectional	Cognitive frailty	>70 years	Mini-Mental State Examination
Liu et al. 2022 ^[21]	Prospective	Incident cognitive impairment	>65 years	Mini-Mental State Examination
Ma et al. 2021 ^[22]	Cross-sectional	Cognitive impairment	60> years	Mini-Mental State Examination
Pohlhausen et al. 2016 ^[23]	Cross-sectional	All dementia	>70 years	Interview
Tseng et al. 2019 ^[24]	Retrospective	Cognitive frailty	>65 years	Mini-Mental State Examination, Montreal Cognitive Assessment
Won et al. 2017 ^[25]	Cross-sectional	Mild cognitive decline	>60 years	Mini-Mental State Examination

Table 2. Quality assessment of the included studies.

Reference	Selection	Compatibility	Outcome	Overall
Cova et al. 2017 ^[18]	4	1	2	7
He et al. 2024 ^[19]	4	2	2	9
Kim et al. 2019 ^[20]	3	2	2	8
Liu et al. 2022 ^[21]	4	2	2	8
Ma et al. 2021 ^[22]	3	2	2	7
Pohlhausen et al. 2016 ^[23]	3	2	2	7
Tseng et al. 2019 ^[24]	3	2	2	7
Won et al. 2017 ^[25]	3	2	2	7

Table 3. Calf circumferences among patients with and without cognitive decline.

Author	Country	CC, patients number/Cognitive decline	Total number of patients	CC, patients number/ Normal	Total number of patients	Results
Cova et al. 2017 ^[18]	Italy	32.9 ± 2.3	24	35.2 ± 2.8	29	Sig, P-value<0.01
He et al. 2024 ^[19]	China	34.04 ± 3.65	121	36.46 ± 2.62	73	Sig, P-value<0.01
Kim et al. 2019 ^[20]	Japan	34.4±2.8	314	34.5±2.8	822	Sig, P-value<0.001
Liu et al. 2022 ^[21]	China	26.8 ± 5.1	828	35.4 ± 6.6	827	Sig, P-value<0.01
Ma et al. 2021 ^[22]	China	32.81 ± 3.20	329	33.93 ± 3.01	1424	Sig, P-value<0.01
Pohlhausen et al. 2016 ^[23]	Germany	33.7 ±4.8	343	35.8 ±4.6	343	Sig, P-value<0.01
Tseng et al. 2019 ^[24]	Taiwan	32.0 ± 3.1	155	33.0 ± 3	369	Not sig. P-value, 0.41
Won et al. 2017 ^[25]	Malaysia	33.2±3.89	331	33.6±3.4	1909	Sig. P-value, 0.32

CC: Calf circumference

Results:

Characters of the included studies:

The current meta-analysis included 8 studies and 8241 patients [18-225]. There were 8 studies, six cross-sectional, one prospective cohort, and one retrospective study, six were from Asia and two from Europe.

The study found a negative association of calf circumference with dementia, MD, -2.38. 95% CI, -4.23 to -.052, and P-value for overall effect, 0.01, Z score=2.51. However, substantial heterogeneity was evident, I^2 for heterogeneity, 99%, P-value<0.00001. The chi-square was 659.52. The negative association of calf circumference and dementia remained robust after removing the study with the highest heterogeneity, MD, -1.23. 95% CI, -1.48 to -.97, and P-value for overall effect <0.001, and Z score=9.48. No significant heterogeneity was found $I^2= 22%$, P-value, 0.28. The chi-square was 3.83. Figure 2 (A-C).

Figure 2 (A). Calf circumferences among patients with and without cognitive decline.

Figure 2 (B). Calf circumferences among patients with and without cognitive decline.

Figure 2 (C). Calf circumferences among patients with and without cognitive decline (Removing outliers).

Discussion:

The study found a negative association of calf circumference with dementia, MD, -2.38. 95% CI, -4.23 to -.052. The negative association of calf circumference and dementia remained robust after removing the study with the highest heterogeneity, MD, -1.23. 95% CI, -1.48 to -.97.

Calf circumference (CC) is a convenient and simple measurement of muscle mass and sarcopenia, in addition, CC was studied as an indicator of malnutrition in particular among the elderly. Furthermore, previous meta-analyses found an association between CC and mortality [26, 27]. However, no meta-analysis has assessed its association with dementia.

Anthropometric measurements for obesity including body mass index, waist circumference, and thigh circumferences have many limitations. Body mass index might be inaccurate in muscular people, in addition, it ignores the distribution of fat and cannot differentiate between fat-free mass and fat mass [28].

Waist circumference, a good indicator of central adiposity is poor regarding the assessment of nutritional status and muscle retention. While the waist-hip ratio might mask central obesity in case of high hip circumference [29-32]. Calf circumference is a simple convenient measurement of peripheral adiposity, nutritional status, and muscle maintenance. Therefore, calf circumference is closer than body mass index as a predictor of cognitive decline and dementia.

Body mass index as a predictor of dementia differs in midlife and late life because underweight is associated with dementia in both mid and late life, while overweight is associated with dementia in midlife and protective in late life [33, 34]. The same applies to waist circumference, WC was associated with dementia among individuals ≥ 65 years in contrast to other age groups [35].

The association between body mass index, waist circumference, and dementia is not linear; a recent meta-analysis found that weight loss is associated with dementia, while upper normal body mass index seems to be protective. Similarly, those in the upper fifth normal waist showed no significant increase in dementia, while weight loss and gain were associated with a significant increase in all-cause dementia and vascular dementia respectively [36]. Because of the above, calf circumference is a good predictor of dementia compared to other anthropometric measures.

This is the first meta-analysis to assess calf circumference as a predictor of dementia. We found a significant negative association between calf circumference and dementia; calf circumference is reflecting muscle mass and avoids the obesity paradox observed when using body mass index and waist circumference [30, 31]. The obesity paradox is the contradicting findings regarding the association of obesity measured by anthropometric measures other than calf circumference; some studies concluded the positive association between obesity and dementia, while other studies observed a protective effect [37, 38]. The positive effects of nutritional status and muscle retention on cognition might explain the obesity paradox. In addition, the high insulin-like growth factor and leptin among obese patients exert neuroprotection and anti-inflammatory effects [39, 40]. The protective effect of CC on cognitive function is

mediated by muscle and subcutaneous fat. Interestingly, when cognition declines memory and place orientation are the first to be involved^[41]. The regulatory effect of the vestibular reflex on neurocognitive function might explain the relationship between CC, memory, and location orientation^[42]. The current results imply that high CC might slow brain changes of cognitive impairment including neuropathological burden and temporal lobe atrophy^[43-44]. Calf circumference assessment may add value to screening tools for cognitive decline.

The shared pathogenic pathways including inflammation and malnutrition explain the association between calf circumference and dementia^[45, 46]

The findings of this meta-analysis are supported by recent observational studies showing a consistent association between lower calf circumference and poorer cognitive outcomes. Liu et al.⁴⁷ and Wu et al.⁴⁸ reported that higher calf circumference was associated with a lower risk of cognitive impairment, supporting a protective role of preserved muscle mass. Similarly, Nie et al.⁴⁹ found a positive but non-linear relationship between calf circumference and global cognition, particularly among individuals with lower calf circumference and among women. At the population level, Feng et al.⁵⁰ observed that increased cognitive impairment prevalence following COVID-19 coincided with declining mean calf circumference in older adults. Together, these findings support calf circumference as a simple, accessible marker of physical frailty and potential cognitive vulnerability.

The current study limitations were the small number of included studies and the high heterogeneity observed.

Clinical implications:

Lower calf circumference may serve as a simple, low-cost, and non-invasive marker for identifying older adults at increased risk of cognitive impairment and dementia. Routine measurement in clinical and community settings could support early risk stratification, prompt further cognitive evaluation, and guide interventions such as exercise and nutritional support aimed at preserving both muscle and cognitive health, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Conclusion: Calf circumference is negatively associated with cognitive decline; the inclusion of various types of cognitive dysfunction (mild cognitive decline, cognitive fragility, and Alzheimer disease) limited the current findings. Further studies focusing on calf circumference/waist circumference ratio are needed.

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